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Assessment Of Radiation Dose Rates Of Facilities Handling Oilfield Chemicals And Products In Southern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Radiation dose rates of facilities handling oilfield chemicals and products in southern Nigeria were recorded through *in-situ* measurements of exposure rates using calibrated Radalert-100 and Digilert-200 radiation meters with Garmin GPS72 receiver for coordinates. Exposure readings in mRh^{-1} and GPS coordinates were taken at thirty-four Lots within three facilities. The probe (Caesium-137) of the exposure meter was held at 1.0m above each sample Lot with their alpha window facing the chemical/product sample and the exposure reading was taken 60 seconds after the meter was switched ON. The exposure rates measured were used in determining the radiological health risks from mathematical models. The lowest and highest exposure levels were measured at the crude oil Lot and the subsea biocide Lot as $0.006 \pm 0.001 \text{ mRh}^{-1}$ and $0.028 \pm 0.012 \text{ mRh}^{-1}$ respectively. 44% of the measurements were consistently higher than ICRP limit value, 0.013 mRh^{-1} . The mean Annual Effective Dose Equivalent (AEDE) of 94.10 ± 35.28 , 106.00 ± 17.66 and $113.40 \pm 24.15 \mu\text{Svy}^{-1}$ were obtained from Production Facility C, Warehouse A and Warehouse B respectively, both higher than the ICRP (2003) indoor limit, $70.0 \mu\text{Svy}^{-1}$ and outdoor limit, $85.0 \mu\text{Svy}^{-1}$. The Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk (ELCR) at all three facilities exceed the recommended 0.29×10^{-3} . The result of this work generally reveal radiation pollution in the facilities which may have negative health impact on people and environment.

Keywords: Exposure, Dose Rate, Oilfields, Radalert, Lifetime cancer, Environment.

1. INTRODUCTION

The human environment is constantly exposed to ionizing radiation from different sources that are both natural and artificial sources. Natural sources include cosmic rays and naturally occurring radioactive materials (NORM) within the earth crust brought to the surface through various weathering processes. Artificial sources include man-made activities such as x-ray equipment that are used in industrial, health care and security applications, and oil and gas exploration activities.

McLennan in 1904 first reported NORM as being associated with oil and gas production. Researches in the 1970s to 1990s such as Kolb et al., 1985; UKOOA, 1985 and API, 1992; have further established NORM presence from oilfield activities as well as ^{238}Ra and ^{222}Rn as the radionuclides of interest. Most studies attribute elevated background ionizing radiation (BIR) to mobilized radionuclide from oil bearing rocks that are eventually deposited on oil pipes (Azionu et al., 2019) or crude oil spillages within oil producing areas (Audu et al., 2019). However, few studies such as Broni-Bediako and Amorin (2010) in

assessing health impact to workers of fumes from drilling mud, recognized the contribution from the chemicals themselves used in oilfield activities but often attribute such health effects to benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene (BTEX) even though radionuclide like radon is known to have similar health effect (Jonas et al., 2018). Oilfield chemicals are used in exploration and production activities such as drilling mud mixing and circulation, drilling cuttings treatment, chemical injection into production processes, performing hydrocarbon sampling, storage tank entry for cleaning and inspection, chemical storage and handling, fluids circulation and sampling. These activities expose the oilfield workers and the environment to these chemicals and their fumes. Ekpo et al., (2025) in the radiometric survey of oilfield chemicals and products in southern Nigeria, had established that Reverse Demulsifier, Triethylene Glycol, Hydrogen Sulphide Scavenger, Subsea Biocide and Scale Inhibitor, which are chemicals commonly used in the oilfield treatment processes of crude oil and condensates are associated with high levels of ionizing radiation that may be unsafe to people and the environment.

Oilfield workers may be exposed to the radiological hazards associated to these chemicals while performing these oilfield activities because the protections provided for handling these chemicals are based on their chemical toxicity without a consideration for their radiological impacts. Radiation exposure could lead to acute health effects such as neurovascular syndrome from high doses of short duration (Hall and Giaccia, 2012). It could also cause chronic effects such as cataracts from moderate doses of long duration (Hammer et al., 2020). The objectives of this research are to measure the radiation exposure rates at the selected oilfield facilities in southern Nigeria, evaluate the radiological health risk parameters of the facilities using radiation models and produce radiation contour maps of the facilities. This work will help in identifying radiologically impacted facilities, improve control of radiation impacted work areas, and contribute to better radiation monitoring of workers.

The study area (Fig. 1) is the Southern Nigerian coastal oilfield area which extends from the Bight of Bonny on longitude 8.0°E to the Bight of Benin on longitude 2.0°E; and overlaying 30 Km offshore the Atlantic Ocean up to 70 Km onshore Nigerian coastline. Facility A is an onshore warehouse at Onne Port, southeast Nigeria, where drilling chemicals and products are stored in Lots identified by the names of the stored samples. Facility B is an onshore warehouse at Ladol Port, southwest Nigeria, where drilling chemicals and products are stored in Lots identified by the names of the stored samples. Production Facility C is an offshore warehouse at a Terminal where production chemicals and products are stored in Lots identified by the names of the stored samples

Fig. 1: Geographic Information System map of the Study Area

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Radalert-100 and Digilert-200 nuclear radiation meters together with Garmin GPS72 Global Positioning System (GPS) Receiver, were used simultaneously for the in-situ measurements at all 34 locations within the two warehouses and one Production Facility to cover all the ranges for alpha, beta and gamma radiations.

2.2 Methods of Data Collection

The nuclear radiation meters were selected based on their design as low radiation level survey meters in indoor and outdoor environments; and were calibrated to measure sensitivity of 0.001 mRh⁻¹ and accuracy of ±10% with ¹³⁷Cs (Rangaswamy *et al.*, 2016). The meters were set to the mRh⁻¹ mode before measurement, then were held at 1.0m above the sample Lot with their alpha windows facing the chemical/product sample and the exposure readings were taken 60 seconds after the meters were switched ON.

The Garmin GPS72 Receiver was switched ON at each of the 34 locations where in-situ measurements were taken and held up front with the top of the unit tilted upward for about 1 minute after accessing the GPS information page on the unit. The northing and easting coordinates of the current location were read off in dddd° mm'mm.m" format.

2.3 Radiological Health Hazard Indices

Three radiological hazards indices were computed to assess the risk associated with public or occupational exposure occurring within the three oilfield facilities with potential of an irradiated environment (Akhtar *et al.*, 2005) due to the presence of these chemicals and products. The indices and their computational models are presented below in Equations 1, 2 and 3.

Absorbed Dose (D)

The radiation absorbed dose is the energy absorbed or deposited per unit mass of an organ or tissue. It is measured in grays. The outdoor exposure rate in μRh⁻¹ was converted to absorbed dose using Equation 1 below:

$$D(\mu\text{Rh}^{-1}) = 8.7\text{nGyh}^{-1} \quad (1)$$

Annual Effective Dose Equivalent (AEDE)

The evaluated absorbed dose was used to calculate the annual effective dose equivalent (AEDE) received by people (workers) in the surveyed area. The dose conversion factor, Co = 0.7 Sv/Gy was used to convert from absorbed dose in air to effective dose received by adult population (UNSCEAR, 2000); and the occupancy factor Ocf = 0.25 for exposure in calculating AEDE, using the equation given below (Rangaswamy *et al.*, 2016; Muhammad *et al.*, 2014; Ononugbo and Mgbemere, 2016):

$$\text{AEDE (mSvy}^{-1}\text{)} = D \times h \times \text{Ocf} \times \text{Co} \quad (2)$$

Where D is the absorbed dose, and h is the time in hours for 1 year (8760h).

Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk (ELCR)

The Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk measures cancer risk induced by exposure to ionizing radiations. ELCR is calculated using equation 3, below:

$$\text{ELCR} = \text{AEDE} \times \text{ADL} \times \text{RFR} \quad (3)$$

Where ADL is the average duration of life (life expectancy) in Nigeria, which is 55 years (WHO, 2023), and RFR is the risk factor given as 0.05 (UNSCEAR, 2000).

3. RESULTS

3.1 In-situ measurement of exposure rates in facilities handling Oilfield Chemicals and Products

The in-situ measurement of background ionizing radiation or exposure rates in facilities handling oilfield chemical and product samples are presented in Tables 1 for Warehouse A and Warehouse B; and Table 3 for Production Facility C. Exposure Rates vary from 9 to 16 μRh^{-1} for Warehouse A, 8 to 20 μRh^{-1} for Warehouse B, and 6 to 28 μRh^{-1} for Production Facility C.

Table 1: Measured In-situ Exposure Rates of Warehouse A and Warehouse B

S/N	Sampling Point	Sampling Code	Coordinate	Exposure Rate (μRh^{-1})
WAREHOUSE A				
1	Bentonite LOT	BEL1	N040 43' 28.5" E0070 09' 22.0"	9.0
2	Barite LOT	BAL1	N040 43' 25.0" E0070 09' 21.6"	12.0
3	Class G Cement LOT	CCL1	N040 43' 28.2" E0070 09' 22.4"	13.0
4	Blasting Grit LOT	BGL1	N040 43' 25.7" E0070 09' 22.1"	12.0
5	Natural Polymer LOT	NPL1	N040 43' 25.1" E0070 09' 21.7"	16.0
6	Synthetic Polymer LOT	SPL1	N040 43' 25.2" E0070 09' 21.8"	12.0
7	Produced Sediment LOT	PSL1	N040 43' 25.4" E0070 09' 19.7"	9.0
8	Coffee Waste LOT	CWL1	N040 43' 25.9" E0070 09' 21.6"	15.0
WAREHOUSE B				
9	Bentonite LOT	BEL2	N060 25' 03.7" E0030 22' 17.2"	13.0
10	Barite LOT	BAL2	N060 25' 02.8" E0030 22' 18.0"	14.0
11	Class G Cement LOT	CCL2	N060 25' 03.9" E0030 22' 18.3"	14.0
12	Blasting Grit LOT	BGL2	N060 25' 02.3" E0030 22' 17.3"	14.0
13	Natural Polymer LOT	NPL2	N060 25' 02.6" E0030 22' 17.2"	16.0
14	Synthetic Polymer LOT	SPL2	N060 25' 03.6" E0030 22' 17.5"	8.0
15	Produced Sediment LOT	PSL2	N060 25' 04.0" E0030 22' 17.1"	14.0
16	Coffee Waste LOT	CWL2	N060 25' 04.1" E0030 22' 16.8"	20.0

Table 2: Calculated Radiological Parameters of Warehouse A and Warehouse B

S/N	Sampling Point	Sampling Code	Coordinate	Exposure Rate (μRh^{-1}) ¹⁾	Absorbed Dose (nGyh^{-1})	Annual Effective Dose AEDE (μSvy^{-1})	Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk, ELCR (10^{-3})
WAREHOUSE A							
1	Bentonite LOT	BEL1	N04043'28.5" E0070 09'22.0"	9.0	73.9	75.6	0.208
2	Barite LOT	BAL1	N04043'25.0" E0070 09'21.6"	12.0	104.4	106.7	0.293
3	Class G Cement LOT	CCL1	N04043'28.2" E0070 09' 22.4"	13.0	113.1	115.6	0.318
4	Blasting Grit LOT	BGL1	N040 43' 25.7" E0070 09' 22.1"	12.0	100.1	102.3	0.281
5	Natural Polymer LOT	NPL1	N040 43' 25.1" E0070 09' 21.7"	16.0	139.2	213.4	0.587
6	Synthetic Polymer LOT	SPL1	N040 43' 25.2" E0070 09' 21.8"	12.0	104.4	106.7	0.293
7	Produced Sediment LOT	PSL1	N040 43' 25.4" E0070 09' 19.7"	9.0	78.3	120.0	0.330
8	Coffee Waste LOT	CWL1	N040 43' 25.9" E0070 09' 21.6"	15.0	126.2	129.0	0.354
WAREHOUSE B							
9	Bentonite LOT	BEL2	N060 25' 03.7" E0030 22' 17.2"	13.0	113.1	115.6	0.318
10	Barite LOT	BAL2	N060 25' 02.8" E0030 22' 18.0"	14.0	117.5	120.1	0.330
11	Class G Cement LOT	CCL2	N060 25' 03.9" E0030 22' 18.3"	14.0	117.5	120.1	0.330
12	Blasting Grit LOT	BGL2	N060 25' 02.3" E0030 22' 17.3"	14.0	117.5	120.1	0.330
13	Natural Polymer LOT	NPL2	N060 25' 02.6" E0030 22' 17.2"	16.0	134.9	137.8	0.379
14	Synthetic Polymer LOT	SPL2	N060 25' 03.6" E0030 22' 17.5"	8.0	65.3	66.7	0.183
15	Produced Sediment LOT	PSL2	N060 25' 04.0" E0030 22' 17.1"	14.0	117.5	120.1	0.330
16	Coffee Waste LOT	CWL2	N060 25' 04.1" E0030 22' 16.8"	20.0	169.7	260.0	0.715
World Standard, ICRP (2003)				13.0	60.0	70.0	0.290

Figure 2: Comparison of Exposure Rate at Warehouses A and B with ICRP Limit

Figure 3: Comparison of Calculated Absorbed Dose at Warehouses A and B with ICRP Limit

Figure 4: Comparison of Annual Effective Dose at Warehouses A and B with ICRP Limit

3.2 Modelled Radiological Health Hazard Parameters

The radiological health hazard parameters calculated from in-situ measurements of exposure rates within the facilities, are presented in Table 2 for Warehouse A and Warehouse B; and Table 4 for the Production Facility C. The Exposure Rate (μRh^{-1}), Absorbed Dose (D), Annual Effective Dose Equivalent (AEDE), and Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk (ELCR) are compared with the world standards values in Figures 2, 3, 4 and 5 respectively for Warehouse A and B; and in Figures 6, 7, 8 and 9 respectively for Production Facility C.

Table 3: Measured In-situ Exposure Rate of Production (FPSO) Facility C

S/N	Sampling Point	Sampling Code	GPS Reading	Exposure Rate (μRh^{-1})
1	Oil-Base Mud LOT	OBL	N030 03' 33.7" E0060 41' 17.2"	6.0
2	Produced Crude LOT	PCL	N030 03' 32.8" E0060 41' 18.0"	6.0
3	Condensate LOT	COL	N030 03' 33.9" E0060 41' 18.3"	12.0
4	Corrosion Inhibitor LOT	CIL	N030 03' 32.3" E0060 41' 17.3"	14.0
5	Scale Inhibitor (Oil) LOT	SIoL	N030 03' 32.6" E0060 41' 17.2"	9.0
6	Scale Inhibitor (Water) LOT	SIwL	N030 03' 33.6" E0060 41' 17.5"	16.0
7	Subsea Biocide LOT	SBL	N030 03' 33.6" E0060 41' 18.8"	28.0
8	Process Biocide LOT	PBL	N030 03' 33.4" E0060 41' 18.2"	9.0
9	Diesel Biocide LOT	DBL	N030 03' 33.6" E0060 41' 18.7"	9.0
10	Reverse Demulsifier LOT	RDT	N030 03' 34.1" E0060 41' 17.1"	16.0
11	Demulsifier LOT	DmL	N030 03' 34.1" E0060 41' 18.9"	13.0
12	Oxygen Scavenger LOT	OST	N030 03' 34.3" E0060 41' 17.1"	9.0
13	H ₂ S Scavenger LOT	HSL	N030 03' 34.5" E0060 41' 18.3"	16.0
14	Tri-ethylene Glycol LOT	TGL	N030 03' 33.6" E0060 41' 18.5"	16.0
15	Acetic Acid LOT	AAL	N030 03' 33.8" E0060 41' 17.4"	15.0
16	Crude Defoamer LOT	CDL	N030 03' 34.2" E0060 41' 17.5"	14.0
17	Chemical Solvent LOT	CSL	N030 03' 34.7" E0060 41' 17.7"	12.0
18	Main Deck	MDk	N030 03' 34.7" E0060 41' 18.7"	15.0

Table 4: Calculated Radiological Hazards of Production (FPSO) Facility C

S/N	Sampling Point	Sampling Code	GPS Reading	Exposure Rate (μRh^{-1})	Absorbed Dose (nGyh^{-1})	Annual Effective Dose AEDE (μSvy^{-1})	Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk, ELCR (10^{-3})
1	Oil-Base Mud LOT	OBL	N030 03' 33.7" E0060 41' 17.2"	6.0	47.9	48.9	0.134
2	Produced Crude LOT	PCL	N030 03' 32.8" E0060 41' 18.0"	6.0	52.2	52.4	0.147
3	Condensate LOT	COL	N030 03' 33.9" E0060 41' 18.3"	12.0	104.4	106.7	0.294
4	Corrosion Inhibitor LOT	CIL	N030 03' 32.3" E0060 41' 17.3"	14.0	121.8	186.7	0.514
5	Scale Inhibitor (Oil) LOT	SIoL	N030 03' 32.6" E0060 41' 17.2"	9.0	74.0	113.0	0.312
6	Scale Inhibitor (Water) LOT	SIwL	N030 03' 33.6" E0060 41' 17.5"	16.0	139.2	213.4	0.587
7	Subsea Biocide LOT	SBL	N030 03' 33.6" E0060 41' 18.8"	28.0	239.3	244.6	0.673
8	Process Biocide LOT	PBL	N030 03' 33.4" E0060 41' 18.2"	9.0	74.0	113.0	0.312
9	Diesel Biocide LOT	DBL	N030 03' 33.6" E0060 41' 18.7"	9.0	78.3	120.0	0.330
10	Reverse Demulsifier LOT	RDT	N030 03' 34.1" E0060 41' 17.1"	16.0	134.9	206.7	0.569
11	Demulsifier LOT	DmL	N030 03' 34.1" E0060 41' 18.9"	13.0	108.8	166.7	0.458
12	Oxygen Scavenger LOT	OST	N030 03' 34.3" E0060 41' 17.1"	9.0	78.3	120.0	0.330
13	H2S Scavenger LOT	HSL	N030 03' 34.5" E0060 41' 18.3"	16.0	134.9	206.7	0.569
14	Tri-ethylene Glycol LOT	TGL	N030 03' 33.6" E0060 41' 18.5"	16.0	134.9	206.7	0.569
15	Acetic Acid LOT	AAL	N030 03' 33.8" E0060 41' 17.4"	15.0	130.5	200.0	0.550
16	Crude Defoamer LOT	CDL	N030 03' 34.2" E0060 41' 17.5"	14.0	121.8	186.7	0.513
17	Chemical Solvent LOT	CSL	N030 03' 34.7" E0060 41' 17.7"	12.0	100.1	153.4	0.422
18	Main Deck	MDk	N030 03' 34.7" E0060 41' 18.7"	15.0	126.2	193.4	0.532
World Standard, ICRP (2003)				13.0	60.0	70.0	0.290

3.3 Radiological Contour mapping of the Sample Sites

The exposure rate contours obtained for the three facilities show that certain areas within these facilities exceed exposure rates limit for public, as such are recommended to be demarcated with a physical restriction along the 0.013mRh^{-1} contour line defining controlled areas to protect people from radiation. The controlled areas may be established at: the bottom right of the contour map of Warehouse A (Figure 10a); the top and bottom left of the contour map of Warehouse B (Figure 10b); and the center right of the contour map of the Production Facility C (Figure 10c).

Figure 9: Comparison of Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk at Production Facility C with ICRP Limit

4. DISCUSSION

The ionizing radiation exposure rate obtained in the facilities handling oilfield chemicals range from 6.0 $\mu\text{R/h}$ to 28.0 $\mu\text{R/h}$. The results showed that 44% of the sampled locations exceeded the ICRP recommended background ionizing radiation exposure level (13 $\mu\text{R/h}$) for the general public. This is similar to the results obtained by Ononugbo *et al* (2011) within industrial areas of ONELGA local government area of Rivers state; and by Ugbede and Benson (2013) for the Emene industrial layout of Enugu state. The mean of the radiation exposure rate that is recorded in Warehouses A and B are high due to non-adherence to the operational procedures used in handling of the chemicals at these Warehouses. As expected, Production Facility C rigorously adherence to operational procedures recorded the lowest mean exposure rates also because of the pressure-tight containment used in Production facility C for storage of the oilfield chemicals.

The calculated absorbed dose range between 47.9 nGy/h to 239.3 nGy/h. The absorbed dose due to ionizing radiation exposure in Warehouses A and B are all above the ICRP recommended indoor limit of 70 nGy/h except in SPL2. Also, the absorbed dose due to ionizing radiation exposure in Production Facility C are all above the ICRP recommended indoor safe limit of 70 nGy/h, except in OBL and PCL. However, absorbed dose at SBL show a value 4 times higher than the safe limit. This result is similar to the result obtained by Audu *et al* (2019) where the value of ionizing radiation exposure rates obtained ranged from 0.007 to 0.040 mR/h^{-1} , with mean that is higher than ICRP standard limit of 0.013 mR/h^{-1} . Hence, the estimated high absorbed doses received in these oilfield storage facilities are attributed to the level of radionuclides enhancement in the oilfield chemicals and products stored or processed within the facilities. The values of all the radiological health hazard parameters computed from the radiation exposure rate show consistently elevated values when compared with world standard limits. This is in line with the findings of Azionu *et al* (2019), where the mean absorbed dose, mean annual effective dose equivalent and the mean excess lifetime cancer risk obtained were $166.73 \pm 89.08 \text{ nGy/h}^{-1}$, $255.60 \pm 136.57 \mu\text{Sv/y}^{-1}$, and $0.70 \pm 0.38 \times 10^{-3}$ respectively, with all these values exceeding their respective world safe limits. However, the study by Azionu *et al* attributed the radiological impact of the pipe storage location to scales deposited on the pipes during crude oil production.

The calculated annual effective dose equivalent due to ionizing radiation exposure in these facilities handling oilfield chemicals and products were found to range from 48.9 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ to 244 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ with the mean of each facility higher than acceptable ICRP limit. However, these values are lower than those obtained by Jonas *et al* (2016) in the radiological survey of the covered and uncovered drilling mud depository, where the ambient dose equivalent rates were 76 nSv/h (665 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$) before and 86 nSv/h (753 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$) after covering the mud. The ambient dose equivalent obtained were attributed to the presence of radon gas released from the drilling mud. The calculated excess lifetime cancer risk due to exposure to ionizing radiation in these oilfield facilities are generally higher than the UNSCEAR and ICRP permissible limit, 0.29×10^{-3} . Typically, ELCR obtained from SBL in-situ measurement show values 5 times higher that permissible limit. This indicates some levels of radiological pollution of the Facilities and a higher probability of workers within these Facilities developing cancer due to exposure to ionizing radiation.

a.) Warehouse A

b.) Warehouse B

c.) Warehouse C

Figure 10: Exposure Rates Contour Mapping of the Selected Facilities Handling Oilfield Chemicals and Products

CONCLUSION

In-situ measurements of exposure rates of selected facilities handling oilfield chemicals and products; and subsequent evaluation of the radiological health risks showed that the exposure rates in the facilities are higher than limit values set by organization such as UNSCEAR and ICRP. The mean values of the Exposure Rates (Figures 2 and 6) and the Annual Effective Dose Equivalent (Figures 4 and 8) obtained are within and slightly elevated above UNSCEAR / ICRP limits. The Absorbed Dose Rate (Figures 3 and 7) and Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk (Figures 5 and 9) significantly exceeded the recommended safe values, indicating that long term exposure of workers of the selected oilfield Facilities may lead to detrimental health impact. The result of this work also revealed from in-situ readings and all radiological hazard parameters a significant background ionizing radiation pollution of the facilities.

We conclude therefore that if no remedial steps are implemented, there are both short-term and long-term health risks to the workers in these facilities handling oilfield chemicals and products. Such remedial steps could include implementation of radiation management controls at some chemical Lots, installation of physical restriction along the 0.013mRh^{-1} contour line to define radiation-controlled areas and dosimetry monitoring for the workers.

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